

CABRISS

NEWSLETTER

Issue: 1

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www.spire2030.eu/cabris

Welcome to the first newsletter of CABRISS project!

The main vision of CABRISS project is to develop a circular economy mainly for the photovoltaic, but also for electronic and glass industry. It will consist in the implementation of: (i) recycling technologies to recover In, Ag and Si for the sustainable PV technology and other applications; (ii) a solar cell processing roadmap, which will use Si waste for the high throughput, cost-effective manufacturing of hybrid Si based solar cells and will demonstrate the possibility for the re-usability and recyclability at the end of life of key PV materials. The developed Si solar cells will have the specificity to have a low environmental impact by the implementation of low carbon footprint technologies and as a consequence, the technology will present a low energy payback (about 1 year).

The originality of the project relates to the cross-sectorial approach associating together different sectors like the Powder Metallurgy (fabrication of Si powder based low cost substrate), the PV industry (innovative PV Cells) and the industry of recycling (hydrometallurgy and pyrometallurgy) with a common aim : make use of recycled waste materials (Si, In and Ag). CABRISS focuses mainly on a photovoltaic production value chain, thus demonstrating the cross-sectorial industrial symbiosis with closed-loop processes.

CABRISS - Implementation of a Circular economy Based on Recycled, reused and recovered Indium, Silicon and Silver materials for photovoltaic and other applications

H2020-WASTE-2014

Starting date: June 1st, 2015

Project duration: 36 months

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CABRISS Kick-off meeting

The CABRISS project kick-off meeting took place at INES (CEA), on 7th and 8th July 2015.

The consortium is based on 16 partners from 9 countries, 6 SMEs, 5 Industries and 5 RTOs working together to reach the project objectives. The main objectives of the project are:

- Developing industrial symbiosis by providing raw materials such as glass or silver pastes as feedstock for other industries (e.g. glass, electronics or metallurgy).
- Collecting up to 90% of the PV waste throughout Europe compared to the 40% rate in 2013.
- Retrieving up to 90% of the high value raw materials from the PV cells and panels: silicon, Indium and silver.
- Manufacturing of PV cells and panels from the recycled raw materials achieving lower cost (25% less) and at least the same performances (i.e. cells efficiency yield) as the conventional processes.
- Involving the EU citizens and industry into such a sustainable and financially viable new economy. Namely, EU PV manufacturing industry will be given a new momentum allowing them to reach 50% of the EU market by 2020 (vs 24% in 2013).

Figure 1. CABRISS project consortium.

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CABRISS at SPIRE-2014 projects

Luc Federzoni and David Pelletier from CEA attended on 29th June 2015 in Brussels an event organized by the PPP SPIRE: INTRODUCING THE SPIRE-2014 PROJECTS - The SPIRE (Sustainable Process Industry through Resource and Energy Efficiency) PPP has been working hard under Horizon 2020 since its official launch in December 2013 and the first fruits of its labours were presented on the afternoon of 29 June as a curtain raiser to the 3rd SPIRE Brokerage event that took place on 30th June 2015. This event gave a valuable snapshot on the objectives and expected deliverables of the first series of SPIRE projects. It was a way to help to create synergies and added value between projects, between various partners, companies, organisations and beyond.

<http://www.spire2030.eu/mediaroom/99/21/Introducing-SPIRE-2014-projects>

CABRISS at EUPVSEC 2015

David Pelletier and Jean-Patrice Rakotoniana from CEA presented the poster “Developing a Circular Economy Based on Recycled, Reused and Recovered Indium, Silicon and Silver Materials for Photovoltaic and Other Applications” at the EU-PVSEC 2015 the largest PV conference in Europe involving researchers and companies from all over the world.

The EU-PVSEC 2015 meeting was an excellent opportunity to present CABRISS project to the broad public in one of the largest conferences in the PV field.

CABRISS
EU PVSEC 2015
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Developing a Circular Economy Based on Recycled, Reused and Recovered Indium, Silicon and Silver Materials for Photovoltaic and Other Applications

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Main project features

- HORIZON 2020 program**
Waste: A Resource to Recycle, Reuse and Recover Raw Materials
WASTE-1-2014 CALL: Moving towards a circular economy through industrial symbiosis
- TYPE OF ACTION:** Innovation actions (EASME)
- Project key features**
Project duration: 36 months (start June 2015)
Budget: € 281,882,25 €
EC Contribution: 7,844,584,54 €
Coordinator: CEA (French Alternative Energies and Atomic Energy Commission)
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CABRISS Genesis

- An important amount of photovoltaic waste
Short term challenge: 17.7 GW installed capacity in Europe have generated around 27 000 tons of waste from installation breakage.
Long term challenge: The total PV products disseminated throughout Europe represent roughly 8 million tons of future PV waste.
- Manufacturing of strategic materials like Ga, In, Ag...
- The European legislation is pushing towards the development of green solution that tackle the issue of PV waste.
The recent WEEE Directive 2012/19/EU provides a legislative framework for extended producer responsibility of PV modules at European scale.

CABRISS Objectives

- CABRISS aims at pioneering a circular economy dedicated to handle the critical situation of recycling the important amount of photovoltaic waste and creating benefits to electronics, metallurgy and glass industries.
- The project has five main objectives:
 - Developing industrial symbiosis by providing raw materials such as glass, silver, plastic as feedstock for other industries (e.g. glass, electronics or metallurgy).
 - Collecting up to 90% of the PV waste throughout Europe compared to the 40% rate in 2013
 - Recovering up to 90% of the high value raw materials from the PV cells and panels: Silicon, Indium and Silver.
 - Manufacturing PV cells and panels from the recycled raw materials at lower cost (25% less) and at least the same performances thanks to the implementation of a solar cell processing roadmap (cost-effective hybrid Si based solar cells).
 - Involving the EU citizens and industries into a sustainable and financially viable new economy. The EU PV manufacturing industry will be given a new momentum allowing them to reach 50% of the EU market by 2020 (vs. 24% in 2013).

CABRISS concept & value chain

CABRISS expected impacts

- Measurable reduction of waste generation and resource use in the medium term
- Significant increase in European and global market up-take and replicability of eco-innovation solutions
- Contribution to standards validated by industrial players and identification of BAT
- Contribution to the EU ETV programme and SPIRE PPP

Partners: CEA, SINTEF, IMEC, RHP, PDS-EP, Leagemeitelsbach, Raahelakrishnan, IMEC, Leuven, Belgium, Vienna University of Technology, RHP Technology, PDS-EP, Innsbruck, Salzburg, Austria, PV Cycle France, Paris, France.

Figure 2. Poster presented in EU-PVSEC 2015

Work in progress: etching of solar cell scrap

At SINTEF laboratory, in Norway, some preliminary results concerning etching of Si scrap were obtained. The goal was to etch away the Si_3N_4 layer as well as the front and back doping layers of pieces of broken solar cells where the front and back contacts already had been etched away. After etching, the scraps will be used as a feedstock for an ingot to be casted in the furnace and to provide 500 g etched scraps to a powdering and sintering experiment.

The challenge was to choose an etching solution with fast enough reaction, and yet not too violent, to be suitable for etching away the layers in relatively large batches.

Four different etch compositions were tested in small scale prior to upscaling of two of the compositions. The goal of the small scale experiments was to identify an etch composition suitable for upscaling.

Further investigations will be carried out.

Figure 3. Photo of the solar cell scrap provided by Loser Chemie.

Figure 4. The small scale experiment with used polish etch (provided by Sintef).

Figure 5. Si ingot grown from Si scrap (provided by Sintef).